

Volatile constituents of *Geranium wallichianum* D. Don ex Sweet. from north-western Himalayan region

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Abstract : The volatile constituents of *Geranium wallichianum* D. Don ex Sweet. of the family Geraniaceae collected from north-western Himalayan region, India was analyzed by capillary GC and GC/MS. The major volatile constituents were germacrene D (28.5%), β -caryophyllene (15.9%) and selinene < 7-*epi*- α > (8.5%) along with δ -cadinene, α -cadinol, linalool, β -bourbonene, γ -amorphene, α -humulene, caryophyllene oxide, isophytol, β -(*E*)-farnesene, (*E,E*) geranyl linalool, terpineol-4-ol, sabinene and cubenol as minor constituents. This is the first report on the essential oil composition of *G. wallichianum* from India.

Keywords : *Geranium wallichianum*, Geraniaceae, essential oil composition, germacrene D, β -caryophyllene, selinene.

Introduction

Geranium wallichianum D. Don ex Sweet. belongs to family Geraniaceae and is commonly known as "Shephred's needles"¹. Flowers of *G. wallichianum* are paired, rose to red purple with pale centre, 2.5–4 cm across. Plant readily distinguished by its large ovate often coloured stipules. Sepals bristly-haired on veins; stamen filaments 5–7 mm. Leaves mostly 4–8 cm across, 3–5 lobed the lobes broad-rhombic often with a fine point and further lobed and toothed; stems much branched 30–120 cm. Calyx with glandular hair. A sepals, including awn like tip, not more than 9 mm long². It is a tall, much branched procumbent or erect perennial herb found in the Himalayas, from Kashmir to Nepal at the altitude of 7000–11000 feet. The herb possesses the astringent properties of the genus to a marked degree. The root stock is used as an alternate to that of *Cotis teeta* wall in eye troubles. The herb is also used in the treatment of toothache³. The rhizomes of the plant are used to treat ulceration, dysentery, diarrhoea, Hemorrhage and leucorrhoea⁴. There is one report on the chemical constituents and antioxidant activity of the extract of whole plant of *G. wallichianum*³. So far, no work has been reported on essential oil composition of *Geranium wallichianum*. Therefore, the aim of the present investigation is to analyze essential oil composition of *G. wallichianum* collected from north-west Himalaya.

Results and discussion

Essential oil composition :

The GC and GC/MS analysis of essential oil of *G. wallichianum* collected from Nainital (Uttarakhand) showed the presence of 68 compounds, of which 43 compounds were identified representing 95.7% of the total oil. Germacrene D (28.5%), β -caryophyllene (15.9%) and selinene < 7-*epi*- α > were identified as major constituents along with δ -cadinene (3.6%), α -cadinol (3.0%), linalool (3.0%), β -bourbonene (2.5%), γ -amorphene (2.5%), α -humulene (2.5%), caryophyllene oxide (2.3%) and isophytol (2.1%) as minor constituents. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on the essential oil composition of *G. wallichianum* from India. However, six compounds were identified as ursolic acid, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol galactoside, herniarin and 2,4,6-trihydroxy ethyl benzoate from the extract of the whole plant of *G. wallichianum*³.

Materials and methods :

Plant collection and identification :

The fresh aerial parts of *Geranium wallichianum* were collected from Kilbury in Nainital (Uttarakhand, India). *G. wallichianum* plant was in full blooming stage. The botanical identification of the specimen was done at Botany Department, Kumaun University, Nainital and submitted to Botanical Survey of India, Dehradun.

Table 1. Essential oil composition of aerial parts of *Geranium wallichianum*

Table-1 (contd.)

Sr. no.	Compds. ^a	Retention time (min)	RI ^b	RI ^c	Percent in oil
1.	α -Pinene	3.172	931	924	1.0
2.	Camphene	3.399	946	946	0.1
3.	Sabinene	3.749	969	969	1.8
4.	β -Pinene	3.839	975	974	0.9
5.	Myrcene	3.973	984	988	0.2
6.	<i>p</i> -Cymene	4.697	1020	1020	0.8
7.	Limonene	4.788	1023	1024	0.2
8.	β - <i>cis</i> -Ocimene	5.157	1039	1032	0.1
9.	γ -Terpinene	5.468	1052	1054	0.5
10.	Terpinolene	6.226	1084	1086	0.2
11.	Linalool	6.501	1095	1095	3.0
12.	Terpineol-4-ol	8.942	1173	1174	1.8
13.	α -Terpineol	9.390	1187	1186	1.4
14.	Geraniol	11.630	1249	1249	0.2
15.	α -Cubebene	15.161	1342	1345	0.1
16.	α -Ylangene	16.005	1364	1373	t
17.	α -Copaene	16.181	1369	1374	0.9
18.	β -Bourbonene	16.546	1378	1387	2.5
19.	β -Elemene	16.824	1385	1389	0.4
20.	α -Gurjunene	17.497	1402	1409	0.1
21.	β -Caryophyllene	17.957	1414	1417	15.9
22.	β -Copaene	18.256	1421	1430	0.5
23.	Isogermacrene D	18.822	1436	FFNSC1.3	0.3
24.	α -Humulene	19.201	1446	1452	2.5
25.	β -(<i>E</i>)-Farnesene	19.366	1450	1454	1.9
26.	Germacrene D	20.374	1476	1484	28.5
27.	γ -Amorphene	20.766	1486	1495	2.5
28.	α -Muurolene	21.040	1493	1478	0.8
29.	(<i>E</i>), (<i>E</i>)- α -Farnesene	21.378	1501	1505	1.5
30.	Selinene < 7- <i>epi</i> - α >	21.727	1511	1520	8.5
31.	δ -Cadinene	21.944	1516	1522	3.6
32.	Germacrene B	23.135	1548	1559	0.1
33.	(<i>E</i>)-Nerolidol	23.462	1556	1561	0.3
34.	Caryophyllene oxide	24.138	1574	1582	2.3
35.	Viridiflorol	24.494	1583	1592	0.2
36.	Humulene epoxide II	25.108	1600	1608	0.2
37.	Cubenol	26.331	1634	1645	1.5
38.	α -Cadinol	26.839	1647	1652	3.0
39.	Intermedeol	27.282	1660	1665	0.8
40.	Phytone	33.416	1835	FFNSC1.3	0.2
41.	Isophytol	36.805	1938	1946	2.1
42.	(<i>Z</i>), (<i>Z</i>)-Geranyl linalool	37.406	1957	1960	0.5

43.	(<i>E</i>), (<i>E</i>)-Geranyl linalool	39.361	2019	2026	1.8
44.	n.i.	-	-	-	2.7
Total					95.7

^aMode of identification : Retention Index, co-injection with standards/Peak enrichment with known oil constituents. ^bRetention indices determined on the Equity-5 column using an *n*-alkane homologous series (C₉-C₃₃). ^cRetention indices from the literature⁵. Bold type indicates major components, t = trace (< 0.1%); n.i. = not identified.

Isolation of essential oil :

The essential oil was extracted from fresh aerial parts of *Geranium wallichianum* by hydrodistillation, for 3 h using a Clevenger apparatus. The percentage essential oil content (0.02% v/w) was estimated on a fresh weight basis. The obtained oil sample was dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate and kept in a cool and dark place before analyses.

Analysis of the essential oil :

The oil was analyzed by using a Shimadzu 2010 Autosystem GC. The column temperature was programmed at 80 °C (hold time for 2 min) to 210 °C (hold time 5 min) at 3 °C min⁻¹ and then 210–300 °C at 3° min⁻¹ and then 210–300 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹ with final hold time of 15 min using N₂/Air at 30.0 ml/min column head pressure as carrier gas, the injector temperature was 270 °C and detector (FID, Flame ionization detector) temperature –280°. The GC/MS used was Autosystem 2010 GC (Rtx – 5.30 mm × 0.25 mm, i.d. FID 0.25 μm) coupled with Shimadzu Q P 2010 plus with thermal desorption system T D 20 with (Rtx-5) fused silica capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm with film thickness – 0.25 μm). The column temperature was 80 °C (hold time for 2 min) to 210 °C (hold time 5 min) at 3 °C min⁻¹ and then 210–300° at 20 °C min⁻¹ with final hold time of 21 min, using helium as carrier gas. The injector temperature was 230 °C and 0.2 μL in *n*-hexane, with split ratio of 1 : 30 MS were taken at 70 eV with a mass range of 40–650 amu.

Identification of the components :

Identification of constituents were done on the basis of Retention Index (RI, determined with reference to homologous series of *n*-alkanes (C₉-C₃₃, Polyscience Corp.,

Niles IL) under identical experimental condition), co-injection with standards (Sigma and known essential oil constituents (standard isolates)), MS Library search (NIST : NIH version 2.1, FFNSC1.3 and Wiley : 7th edition), by comparing with the MS literature data⁵. The relative amounts of individual components were calculated based on GC peak area (FID response) without using correction factor.

Conclusions

The analysis of essential oil of *Geranium wallichianum* D. Don ex Sweet. collected from Kilbury in Nainital (Uttarakhand, India) showed the presence of germacrene D (28.5%), β -caryophyllene (15.9%) and selinene < 7-*epi*- α > (8.5%) as major constituents. So, from the above discussion, it is concluded that the plant *Geranium wallichianum* can prove to be a good source of germacrene D for commercial purpose.

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